

Long-term water quality responses to sediment removal in a small, shallow, urban lake

Laura H. Härkönen^{a,*}, Antti Taskinen^a, Olga Tammeorg^b, Anna-Lena Granlund-Blomfelt^c

^a Finnish Environment Institute, Latokartanonkaari 11, FI-00790 Helsinki, Finland

^b Department of Agricultural Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture and Forestry, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 27, (Latokartanonkaari 5), FI-00014, Finland

^c City of Kauniainen, Environmental department, Kauniaistentie 10, FI-02700 Kauniainen, Finland

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ABSTRACT

Sediment removal is a promising strategy for lake restoration that potentially provides long-lasting water quality improvement by directly tackling the source of internal phosphorus (P) loading. However, more studies evaluating the longevity of intervention results are needed to viably assess the method's restoration performance. We used long-term data to evaluate the water quality impacts of sediment removal in small, shallow Lake Galträsk in southern Finland, where sediment removal by suction dredging was conducted in 2009–2011. The top 50–100 cm of surface sediment was removed from 18 % of the lake's total area to increase the lake depth for recreational purposes. Data before and after sediment removal were analyzed using a combination of structural break and interrupted time series analyses. Our results revealed a significant reduction in the water column P concentration after sediment removal, suggesting that lake recovery from past loading was substantially promoted by the intervention. Additionally, suspended solid concentration reduced after sediment removal, enabling favorable conditions for submerged macrophyte recolonization. Water color and chemical oxygen demand increased after the intervention, possibly due to both internal and external drivers. Nitrogen (N), in turn, was not unaffected by the sediment removal, and the N/P ratio subsequently increased. The long-term changes in water quality and submerged macrophyte abundance after suction dredging have resulted in the absence of harmful algal blooms. Our results demonstrate that sediment removal can enable the long-term recovery of lakes from legacy P loading and act as a powerful measure to mitigate eutrophication.

1. Introduction

Nutrient enrichment and subsequent eutrophication are among the main reasons for water quality impairment in lakes, highlighting the need to focus management on nutrient stress (Birk et al., 2020; Downing, 2014). The degradation of lakes negatively impacts biodiversity, together with ecosystem health, and may increase lacustrine greenhouse gas emissions (Beaulieu et al., 2019; Chislock et al., 2013; Morales-Williams et al., 2021). Additionally, eutrophication-induced harmful algal blooms (HABs) threaten the vital ecosystem services to society offered by freshwaters, including the provision of drinking water, recreation, and tourism (Reynaud and Lanzanova, 2017). HABs increase in magnitude and frequency with increasing nutrient pollution and are at risk of intensifying due to global warming and summer droughts (Richardson et al., 2018).

International policies and initiatives such as the Sustainable

Development Goals of the United Nations (UN), the Water Framework Directive (WFD) together with the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) in the European Union (EU), and the Clean Water Act in US drive the protection and restoration of lakes and other aquatic ecosystems. Despite major efforts that have been undertaken to reduce loading and restore aquatic ecosystems, lakes still largely suffer from excess nutrients from both external and internal sources (e.g., Carvalho et al., 2019; Poikane et al., 2024). While the reduction of external loading is often a crucial step towards managing lake water quality, in-lake interventions are also an important approach in restoring lakes (Tammeorg et al., 2024a). In-lake methods often aim to improve water quality by increasing the retention of limiting nutrients, especially phosphorus (P), for example by P inactivation or artificial oxygenation (e.g. Beutel and Horne, 1999; Huser et al., 2016; Sarvala et al., 2020). However, these in-lake measures have been claimed as ineffective at tackling legacy phosphorus (e.g., Horppila, 2019).

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: laura.harkonen@syke.fi (L.H. Härkönen).

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One of the promising strategies for nutrient recovery is sediment removal, which may eliminate the necessity for repeated interventions by directly targeting P accumulated in lake sediments (Cooke et al., 2005; Peterson, 1982; Pierce, 1970). Numerous reviews (Abell et al., 2022; Bormans et al., 2016; Cooke et al., 2005; Lürling et al., 2020) and a recent meta-analysis (Wan et al., 2025) on the impacts of sediment removal have been published, with many of them demonstrating the intervention's ability to reduce internal P loading, and to provide long-term effectiveness in ecological restoration. In many cases, nutrient concentrations in the water column have declined, phytoplankton biomass and cyanobacterial blooms have decreased, and the coverage of submerged macrophytes has increased (Björk et al., 2010; Hassett and Steinman, 2022; Van Wichelen et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2010; Wan et al., 2025). However, negligible impacts on internal P loading have also been reported (Annadotter et al., 1999) and contrasting result longevities of water column P reduction after sediment removal have been observed (Jing et al., 2019; Ruley and Rusch, 2002). There have been insufficient long-term studies to assess the effectiveness of the approach with confidence (Phillips et al., 2020). The lack of documentation may be part of the reason for the limited evidence, which probably also stems from a deficiency of long-term, comprehensive, and inclusive monitoring activities. Consequently, the reliability of evaluations of the success of sediment removal may be limited, thus preventing such studies reaching the scientific literature. Moreover, the overall application of sediment removal in lake restoration is often restrained due to its controversial reputation, resulting from high costs and environmental concerns (Abell et al., 2022; Bormans et al., 2016; Yan and Li, 2023).

Lake Gallträsk is a small, shallow, urban lake in southern Finland that was treated by sediment removal to increase the lake depth for recreational purposes at the beginning of the 2010s. Here, we used available long-term data for the lake to assess the impacts of sediment removal on water quality and on the trophic status of the lake. We hypothesized that the attempt to increase the lake depth simultaneously targeted legacy nutrients in the sediment, with consequent implications for water quality and lake trophic status in the longer term. To test this hypothesis, both the linear and non-linear behavior of changes in water quality before and after sediment removal were analyzed and the

interpretation of results was complemented using available information on biological quality indicators.

2. Methods

2.1. Study lake

Lake Gallträsk is a small, shallow polymictic lake located in the City of Kauniainen, southern Finland (lake number 81.055.1.009, coordinates 6678159,000N, 374466,000E (ETRS89)) (Fig. 1). The lake has a surface area of 11.2 ha, a maximum depth of 1.6 m, and an average depth of 1.0 m. The catchment area (1.12 km²) is dominated by the built environment (63.9 %) and mineral soil forests (25.9 %). At the south-western end of the lake is a 4.6-ha emerged bog, Träskmossen, which was conserved in 1988 and comprises 1.8 % of the catchment area. The remaining 8.5 % of the catchment area consists of the lake itself. The inflow to L. Gallträsk mostly comes from two artificial ditches surrounding the bog, in which management activities were carried out in the mid-2000s. Water from the lake drains through a shallow stream to eutrophic Lake Lippajärvi in the northeast. The estimated hydraulic retention time of L. Gallträsk is 118 days.

The lake suffered from high external nutrient loading due to domestic wastewaters from the early 1920s until the sewage diversion in 1975. Additionally, a battery factory operated in the catchment area from 1941 to 1946. A landfill was also initially located on the southern shore of the lake between 1947 and 1960, after which it was transferred to the western end of the bog and finally terminated in 1965. Historical loading from the battery factory and landfill had partly contaminated the surface sediments with heavy metals (Table 1). Before sediment removal, the surface sediment (top 50 cm) water content was 92 %, loss on ignition (LOI) was 63 %, indicating a high organic matter content, and the dry weight TP content was on average 0.85 mg/g (Maa ja vesi Oy, 1992; Riipi et al., 2002). The estimated annual sedimentation rate in L. Gallträsk before sediment removal was c. 0.1–2.5 mm/a.

Following the cessation of wastewater loading, the average annual loading of TP to L. Gallträsk, simulated with the Water quality and nutrient load model system for Finnish watersheds WSFS-Vemala (Huttunen et al., 2016), has been 26 kg/a and has not varied

Fig. 1. Lake Gallträsk (City of Kauniainen, southern Finland) and its catchment area (a) and a bathymetric map based on radar sounding conducted in 2020 (b), (Suomen maatutkapalvelu, 2020). Dredging areas during 2009–2011, sampling stations for water quality indicators and phytoplankton, transects for macrophyte mapping, and the treatment areas for the removed sludge are indicated. Contains data from the National Land Survey of Finland Topographic Database 11/2024, License CC BY 4.0.

Table 1

Minimum, maximum and average concentrations of heavy metals in the surface sediment (top 0.5 m) of Lake Gallträsk during March 2005 within ($n = 12$) and outside the dredging area ($n = 12$). The values in bold exceed the threshold values set in the national Decree on the assessment of soil contamination (Act 214/2007).

	Location	As	Hg	Cd	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
Min.	Dredging area	<8	<0.2	0.5	10.0	12.0	10.0	14.0	90.0
	Outside the dredging area	<8	<0.2	0.5	10.0	12.0	10.0	16.0	18.0
Max.	Dredging area	<8	<0.2	1	12.0	26.0	11.0	55.0	217.0
	Outside the dredging area	<8	<0.2	0.8	11.0	22.0	11.0	46.0	208.0
Avg.	Dredging area	<8	<0.2	0.8	11.1	19.9	10.8	39.0	171.7
	Outside the dredging area	<8	<0.2	0.6	10.3	18.0	10.4	32.4	134.3
	Threshold values, Act 214/2007	5	0.5	1	100.0	100.0	50.0	60.0	200.0

considerably between the years (Fig. S1). The national, process-based WSFS-Vemala -model simulates nutrient transport from catchments to surface waters, taking into account hydrology, nutrient processes, leaching, and land use (Huttunen et al., 2016). The external TP loading to L. Gallträsk mainly originates from urban stormwaters (89 %), background export from forests (7 %) and deposition (3 %).

2.2. In-lake restoration efforts

Excessive loading of nutrients from wastewaters in the mid-20th century led to severe eutrophication of L. Gallträsk, resulting in abundant cyanobacterial blooms, due to which swimming was occasionally banned. Eutrophication also caused the expansion of macrophytes, especially the yellow waterlily (*Nuphar lutea*), which was also considered to hamper the lake's recreational use. Both the lake itself and its surroundings have high recreational value, which prompted the restoration needs.

2.2.1. Macrophyte removal and biomanipulation

Between 1982 and 1992, annual harvesting of *N. lutea* was conducted to restore lost recreational amenities. During 1992, 2000, 2002, and 2006, efforts to remove excess rhizomes of *N. lutea* by raking were also conducted. Ever since, annual harvesting of vegetation has been conducted in the central part of the lake, covering an area of approx. 7–8 ha.

In 2003, biomanipulation via the removal of benthivorous fish (crucian carp, *Carassius carassius*) was conducted in an attempt to reduce bioturbation and the proliferation of HABs, with a target catch of c. 200 kg/ha and a total of 83 kg/ha fish eventually removed.

2.2.2. Sediment removal

In 2009–2011, suction dredging using a hydraulic Watermaster III -cutter dredge was implemented in the deepest part of L. Gallträsk over an area of approx. 2 ha (corresponding to 18 % of the lake surface area) (Fig. 1). The aim was to increase the lake depth by removing the top 50–100 cm of the sediment. Deepening of the lake was anticipated to primarily benefit recreation, but also to reduce the risk of under-ice hypoxia and limit the overgrowth of floating-leaved macrophytes (Riipi et al., 2002). Prior to sediment removal, experimental suction dredging had been carried out in 2006 in an area of 3500 m², during which a total of c. 1500 m³ sediment was removed (top 50 cm) to test the treatment of sediment slurry in geotextile tubes using a polymer.

The suction dredging in 2009–2011 was conducted outside the growing season (Table 2). In total 26,000 m³ of sediment was removed from the 2-ha dredging area. During the suction dredging, near-bottom water of the lake was continuously mixed with the removed sediment, resulting in a total of 100,000 m³ of sediment slurry, which was transported from the suction head by pumping via pipes to the established treatment areas for processing (Fig. 1). The removed sludge was treated in 17 × 9 m GT500D-geotextile tubes, for which reinforcing mesh and layers of moraine and crushed stone with 40-cm banks were used as foundations (slope of 1–2 %; (Sito-Rakennuttajat, 2012)). The sludge was dewatered in the geotextile tubes using a polyacrylamide-based cationic flocculant (Zetag® 8185, BASF Corporation, USA) as a 0.25 % solution, leaving a total of 6750 m³ of reusable material after treatment

Table 2

Details of suction dredging efforts in Lake Gallträsk from 2006 to 2011. *The dredging during 2006 was small-scale, experimental dredging, based on which the efforts for 2009–2011 were planned.

Time of dredging	Sediment removed (m ³)	Sludge led to geotextile tubes (m ³)	Polymer added (kg)	Water returned to the lake (m ³)	Dewatered sediment (m ³)
8–26 Oct 2006*	1500				
29 Apr to 29 May 2009	8000	32,000	1650	29,000	1650
14 Oct to 7 Dec 2009	8500	31,000	2900	28,000	2900
28 Oct to 10 Dec 2010	5000	19,475	1155	17,630	1155
5–24 May 2011	4500	17,525	1045	15,870	1045
Total	27,500	100,000	6750	90,500	6750

(Table 2; (Sito-Rakennuttajat, 2012)). The filtrate from the geotextile tubes was returned to the lake and the dewatered sediment was mainly used outside the catchment area in landscaping of a slalom slope, as well as in other land construction works. A small amount (approx. 600 m³) of the dewatered sediment was utilized in landscaping of the treatment areas for recreational purposes. Water quality (total phosphorus (TP), phosphate phosphorus (PO₄), total nitrogen (TN), ammonium nitrogen (NH₄), nitrate nitrogen (NO₃), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg), lead (Pb), zinc (Zn)) of the incoming slurry and the filtrate was monitored by sampling.

The total costs for the sediment removal in 2009–2011 were c. €860,000, covering all prior investigations, the environmental permit process and planning, construction of the sediment treatment areas, the dredging, the geotextile tubes and polymer, the reuse of dewatered sediment, and the monitoring of water quality during the intervention. Considering the total expenses, the operating costs per treated ha were thus approx. €430,000 (2-ha dredging area) and approx. €33 €/m³ of sediment removed (26,000 m³ removed in total).

2.3. Water quality data

Data on lake water quality from 1971 to 2024 were obtained from an open national database maintained by the Finnish Environment Institute (License CC BY 4.0) and from the City of Kauniainen. The sampling frequency had varied between years, with the most frequent sampling occurring in conjunction with active in-lake restoration activities, most frequently covering the parameters TN and TP and the months from April to September (Table S1).

Samples had been collected with a tube sampler (Limnos water sampler, Limnos Ltd., Poland) from depths of 0.3–1 m at two sampling locations (Fig. 1). Regular measurements included alkalinity, NH₄, chemical oxygen demand (COD_{Mn}), chlorophyll-*a* (Chl *a*), dissolved

oxygen (O₂), electrical conductivity (EC), pH, PO₄, the sum of nitrite and nitrate nitrogen (NO₂ + NO₃), suspended solids (SS), temperature, TN, TP, turbidity, and water color. During a limited period (2006–2014), water column arsenic (As), Cd, chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), Pb, and Zn had also been monitored. All the water quality analyses had been performed in FINAS-accredited laboratories following standard methods described in Mitikka and Ekholm (2003).

2.4. Biological quality elements

Phytoplankton data for L. Gallträsk were obtained from the open national database of the Finnish Environment Institute (License CC BY 4.0). Annual phytoplankton samples had been taken in July–August 1971, 2008, 2010–2012, 2014, 2016–2017, 2020, 2022 and 2024 as bulk samples from 0 to 1 m depth using a tube sampler (Limnos water sampler, Limnos Ltd., Poland). The samples were preserved with acid Lugol's solution and analyzed using the Utermöhl technique (CEN:15204, 2006).

Macrophytes in L. Gallträsk had been mapped along transects during 2002, 2010, 2011, 2014, 2017, 2022, and 2024 (FCG, 2023; Tantt, 2024). Additionally, some historical macrophyte data were available from the 1940s to 1990s (Barkman, 2003). During 2002–2024, macrophytes had been monitored once during the growing season (July–September) along three transects perpendicular to the shoreline in the southwestern, southern, and northwestern parts of the lake (Fig. 1). Macrophyte species and abundances were recorded from 5-m-wide transects extending 100–280 m from the shoreline and covering depths from 0 to 1.7 m. The abundance indexes were derived from FCG (2023) and Tantt (2024), who had calculated the indexes following (Eq. 1):

$$(d \times c) + (d \times c) + \dots + (d \times c) = \sum_{i=1}^N d_i c_i \quad (1)$$

where, at location i , d is the distance (m) within transect from the previous mapping location, and c is the coverage of macrophytes on the scale 1–7 with 1 representing the coverage <0.5 %, 2 representing 0.5–1 %, 3 representing 1–5 %, 4 representing 6–25 %, 5 representing 26–50 %, 6 representing 51–75 %, and 7 representing 76–100 %, respectively (FCG, 2023; Tantt, 2024). However, vegetation along the transects had been harvested to varying degrees during the inventories in 2011, 2014, and 2017, in addition to which the inventory in 2022 was conducted after harvesting (FCG, 2023). Hence, macrophyte data were only treated as descriptive, and trophic indices following, for example, Penning et al. (2008) were not calculated.

Data on fish abundance and community structure were obtained from an open national database (Natural Resources Institute, License CC BY 4.0) and from the City of Kauniainen. Data were only available for the years 1999 (Riipi et al., 2002), 2014, 2017, and 2020, when random sampling had been conducted with Nordic multi-mesh survey nets following standard methods described in Olin et al. (2002). Each year, six to eight gillnets and two nights were used in sampling. The size of the gillnets was 1.5 × 30 m consisting of 12 panels (2.5 m each) having mesh sizes 5, 6.25, 8, 10, 12.5, 15.5, 19.5, 24, 29, 35, 43 and 55 mm. The catch as number per unit effort (NPUE (ind./net/night)) and biomass per unit effort (BPUE (g/net/night)) was used as an index of fish abundance. Unfortunately, the timing of sampling during the years was not always consistent with the national recommendation of focusing effort on the warmer months (July–September) when fish are most active (Olin et al., 2014). In 2014 and 2017, fish sampling was conducted in late fall, due to which the data must be treated with caution.

Data on benthic invertebrates, diatoms, and zooplankton were not available before and after sediment removal. Based on earlier observations, the swan mussel (*Anodonta cygnea*) has been present in L. Gallträsk (Karvinen, 1997; Riipi et al., 2002), but its abundance and distribution before and after the intervention remain unknown. Additionally,

breeding mallards (*Anas platyrhynchos*) and goldeneyes (*Bucephala clangula*) have earlier been observed on the lake (Karvinen, 1997), but no data on waterfowl abundance before or after sediment removal are available.

2.5. Statistical analyses

To test the impact of sediment removal on water quality, data from 1987 to 2005 were used to describe conditions before the intervention. Data from the period with the highest concentrations in the late 1970s and early 1980s (Fig. 2) were not included to avoid mixing the impacts of past, extreme external loading on the analyses. The period during sediment removal was in 2006–2011, comprising both experimental and active dredging (see section 2.2.2). The data from 2012 to 2024 represented the period after sediment removal, when mechanical perturbation of the sediment no longer occurred. The concentrations of different parameters at the two sampling points (Fig. 1) were similar in all studied periods (before, during, and after sediment removal; Fig. S2), due to which pooled data from these two sampling points were used in statistical analyses. Separate analyses were performed for all annually available data and for data regarding the growing season only (June–September).

To analyze the effects of sediment removal, several established methods for both comparing differences between groups and detecting changes in timeseries data were utilized. Despite their long-term nature, the data were sparse and irregularly dated, consequently setting some restrictions on method selection. The main criterion for the selection of methods was that they had to complement each other. For instance, we chose models for which a moment of interruption in the trends is either given or not, i.e. the model itself looks for the interruptions. Moreover, we selected techniques applicable to non-Gaussian data and favored methods allowing for graphical representation of the results. Consequently, the Wilcoxon rank-sum method, structural break analysis, and the interrupted time series (ITS) method were considered appropriate for the purpose. None of these methods require data with regular intervals and therefore imputation was not needed.

The Wilcoxon rank-sum test is a nonparametric alternative to the two-sample t -test and is based solely on the order in which the observations from the two samples fall (e.g., Milton and Arnold, 1989). It is used for comparing two independent samples of nonnormally distributed data to determine whether they come from the same distribution, which in this case, were water quality parameters before and after dredging.

Structural break analysis is based on the framework of Zeileis et al. (2003), and tests for deviations from stability in the classical linear regression model (Eq. 2)

$$y_i = x_i^T \beta + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where, at time i , y_i is the observation of the dependent variable, x_i is a vector of regressors, with the first component equal to unity, β is a vector of regression coefficients, with the first component as the intercept, and ε_i is the error.

If there are m breakpoints, where the coefficients shift from one stable relationship to a different one, there are $m + 1$ segments in which the regression coefficients are constant, and the model can be rewritten as (Eq. 3)

$$y_i = x_i^T \beta_j + \varepsilon_i \quad (i = i_{j-1} + 1, \dots, i_j, j = 1, \dots, m + 1) \quad (3)$$

where j denotes the segment index. The breakpoints are estimated by minimizing the residual sum of squares of Eq. (3). A crucial feature of the method is that it seeks the breakpoints, i.e., they are not given by the user.

The ITS method can be used when data are available about an outcome over time and one wants to understand whether and how the outcome has changed after one or more interruptions at one or more

Fig. 2. Total phosphorus (TP) concentration in Lake Gallträsk during 1971–2024 presented as the growing season (June–September) averages with standard deviations. Sewage diversion was established in 1975. Sediment removal by suction dredging was conducted in 2009–2011 following small-scale experimental dredging in 2006 and the removal of benthivorous fish in 2003. The colored boxes indicate the threshold values for the ecological status of small humic lakes (Aroviita et al., 2019).

specific points in time. The data need to include observations before and after the interruption, and the more observations there are on both sides, the more robust the model will typically be. We applied a generalized linear model (GLM) based ITS approach, since we wanted to account for the non-Gaussian nature of TP, TN and SS, which are parameters for which estimates of external loading based on WSFS-Vemala-simulations were available (Huttunen et al., 2016). Autocorrelation structures were not considered due to irregular and sparse observations. Because of the long duration of the dredging period (2006–2011), we constructed the ITS model for two interruptions, the first being the beginning of the experimental dredging in 2006 and the second being the end of sediment removal in 2011. By modifying the representation of, for example, Turner et al. (2021), this model can be expressed as Eq. (4):

$$g(y_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{time}_t + \beta_2 \text{interruption1}_t + \beta_3 (\text{time}_t - T_1) \text{interruption1}_t + \beta_4 \text{interruption2}_t + \beta_5 (\text{time}_t - T_2) \text{interruption2}_t + \text{load}_t + \text{season}_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

where y_t represents the outcome (TP, TN and SS concentrations) that is measured at time point t (day), and $g()$ is a logarithmic link function. The first interruption, the beginning of experimental dredging, occurs at time T_1 . The indicator variable interruption1_t represents the post-experimental dredging interval, coded as 0 upto T_1-1 and 1 from T_1 onwards. The second interruption, the first time point t after sediment removal, occurs at T_2 and its indicator variable interruption2_t is coded 0 upto T_2-1 and 1 from T_2 onwards. The model parameters (β values) represent the baseline intercept β_0 , baseline slope β_1 , change in the level at the first interruption β_2 , change in slope β_3 from $T_1 + 1$ onwards, change in the level at the second interruption β_4 , and change in slope β_5 from $T_2 + 1$ onwards. Covariates load_t and season_t represent the external loading and seasonality, respectively. The sums of external loads (kg) of TP, TN and SS during the previous 30 days prior to each observation were obtained from the nutrient loading model WSFS-Vemala (Huttunen et al., 2016). The usage of WSFS-Vemala-simulated external loading as covariates in the ITS analyses allowed for increasing precision in evaluating the impacts of sediment removal and enabled us to eliminate the interference of climate fluctuations on these water quality indicators. WSFS-Vemala simulates lake-specific nutrient transport and leaching from terrestrial ecosystems on a daily time-step for all Finnish watersheds by using an operational hydrological flood forecasting modeling system based on real-time reporting weather stations with daily precipitation and temperature values (Huttunen et al., 2016; Vehviläinen and Huttunen, 2001). The estimated monthly loading was highest in April during snow meltdown, and in October–December during high rainfall and runoff (Fig. S3). Due to the paucity of data, season_t is a factor variable representing only two seasons, namely the baseline level off-growing season (January–May and October–December) and growing season (June–September). Finally, ε_t is the gamma-distributed error

term.

ITS analysis is carried out executing the model described in Eq. (4) in two stages. It is first fitted to the whole time series, and then to the period before dredging/sediment removal, neglecting all the terms related to the interruptions. The results of former run describe the post-dredging water quality. The model of the latter run, in turn, is used to predict water quality in the post-dredging period, assuming that the intervention did not occur. The difference between these simulations represents the effect of sediment removal.

R Statistical Software (v4.4.1; R Core Team, 2024) was employed to perform statistical analyses. The functions `wilcox.test` and `glm` were used for the Wilcoxon test and ITS analysis, respectively. R packages `strucchange` (Zeileis et al., 2002) was used for structural change analysis and packages `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016) and `ggpubr` (Kassambara, 2023) for visualizations.

The available biological quality data before sediment removal were too limited to allow for statistical comparison of the biota of L. Gallträsk before and after the intervention. Instead, biological data were treated as descriptive to support the interpretation of water quality results.

3. Results

3.1. Sludge and filtrate quality

Flocculation in geotextile tubes enabled a substantial reduction of nutrients in the slurry, as 99.6 % of TP and 96.9 % of TN were removed, respectively (Table 3). The TP concentration in the filtrate was close to the average values in the lake before dredging (Table 3, Fig. 2). The concentration of NO_3 , on the other hand, increased considerably in the filtrate assuming a role in nitrification. The sludge diverted for treatment did not contain high amounts of Cd or Hg. However, concentrations of Pb and Zn were high in the sludge but substantially lower in the

Table 3

Concentrations of sludge and filtrate constituents with proportional reductions. The sludge was diverted from Lake Gallträsk in 2009–2011 by suction dredging and led to geotextile tubes for dewatering. The filtrate was returned to the lake.

Parameter	Concentration in sludge	Concentration in filtrate	Reduction (%)
Dry matter (%)	0.91	0.02	98.2
TP ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	9800.0	35.1	99.6
PO_4 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	2270.0	10.2	99.6
TN ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	125,750.0	3900.0	96.9
NH_4 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	1850.0	1190.0	35.7
NO_3 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	27.5	154.0	−462.0
Cd ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	4.0	1.1	72.7
Hg ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	0.4	0.1	85.2
Pb ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	125.0	5.6	95.5
Zn ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	1097.0	27.4	97.5

filtrate.

Based on the total amount of sludge diverted from L. Gallträsk during the dredging in 2009–2011 (approximately 100,000 m³) and the average TP concentration in the sludge (9800 µg/L), the total amount of TP removed from the lake during dredging was c. 980 kg. Following the total cost of the intervention (€860,000, see section 2.2.2), the calculated cost per 1 kg TP removed was c. €878.

3.2. Lake water quality

3.2.1. Concentrations before and after sediment removal

The mean TP of the growing season in Lake Gallträsk displayed the first and most pronounced decline after sewage diversion in 1975 (Fig. 2). Elevated TP concentrations indicative of bad ecological status for shallow humic lakes (Aroviita et al., 2019) were still recorded in the early 1980s. After 1987, the concentrations appeared to stabilize to levels mainly indicating moderate, but occasionally also good ecological status. After the highest sediment removal effort in 2009, the TP concentration of the growing season dropped and has remained on a level indicating good or high ecological status.

Considering all annually available data, the median values for alkalinity and EC together with the concentrations of TP, PO₄, and SS were significantly lower after sediment removal (during, 2012–2024) compared to the period before the intervention (1987–2005) (Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $P < 0.05$) (Table 4, Fig. 3). The median values for COD_{Mn} and color, in turn, were significantly higher after sediment removal.

During the growing season, the median values for alkalinity, EC, and both PO₄ and TP were significantly lower, whereas COD_{Mn} was significantly higher after sediment removal (Table 4, Fig. 3). Additionally, turbidity in the growing season was higher after the intervention, assuming a role of primary production, although the median concentrations of SS and Chl *a* in the growing season were not affected (Table 4, Fig. 3). The average Chl *a* to TP ratio was 0.3 before the intervention and increased to 0.5 during the intervention. Following sediment removal, the average Chl *a* to TP ratio has been 0.4.

Sediment removal did not have an impact on the median concentrations of TN, due to which the median TN to TP ratio experienced a significant increase (Table 4, Fig. 3). The annual median for NO₂₊₃ significantly increased after sediment removal, but the growing season median was not affected.

The limited amount of data available for heavy metals in the water column indicate slight increases in average concentrations after sediment removal (2012–2014) in comparison to the period during the

intervention (2006–2011) for As (average with standard deviation 0.9 ± 0.4 µg/L during and 1.3 ± 0.8 µg/L after, respectively), Cd (0.1 ± 0.0 µg/L during; 0.2 ± 0.4 µg/L after), Pb (0.6 ± 0.2 µg/L during; 1.1 ± 0.8 µg/L after) and Zn (12.9 ± 8.1 µg/L during; 15.6 ± 14.2 µg/L after). The average concentrations of Co (4.2 ± 2.7 µg/L during; 2.0 ± 1.2 µg/L after), Cr (0.8 ± 0.5 µg/L during; 0.6 ± 0.4 µg/L after) and Ni (2.3 ± 1.2 µg/L during; 1.0 ± 0.6 µg/L after), in turn, were slightly lower after sediment removal.

3.2.2. Structural change and ITS analysis results

Consistent with the results of the Wilcoxon rank-sum test (Table 4), the linear regression lines indicated decreasing overall trends for SS, TP, PO₄, and EC and increasing trends for COD_{Mn} and water color during the study period based on all annually available data (dashed black lines in Fig. 4). Additionally, O₂ and pH displayed slightly increasing trends during the study period.

However, the structural break analysis indicated regression discontinuity as structural break points in the data were observed for several parameters (Fig. 4). A breakpoint occurs if the concentration level changes abruptly or its direction changes, i.e., the intercepts and/or slopes of the linear regression differ between the segments. Elevated concentrations at end of the period of sediment removal were observed for COD_{Mn} and color, with reduced rates thereafter. PO₄ and SS increased during the intervention and have declined with reduced rates thereafter. TP declined both before and after treatment, but the observed structural change implies a substantial, abrupt decline in concentrations levels after sediment removal. EC, in turn, showed decreased values at the end of the period of sediment removal, with elevated rates thereafter (Fig. 4), although the Wilcoxon rank-sum test indicated significantly lower EC values after treatment (Table 4).

No structural changes were observed for either Chl *a* or TN, TN/TP, NH₄ and alkalinity based on all annually available data.

Regarding the growing season, in turn, the structural break analysis indicated that Chl *a* abruptly increased during sediment removal but reduced thereafter (Fig. 5). Similarly, PO₄, NH₄, and TN increased during the intervention but declined soon after. Growing season TP did not display structural changes during the study period, but an abrupt increase in the TN to TP ratio occurred at the beginning of the intervention.

Consistent with the results from the structural break analysis, a gradually decreasing trend in the TP concentration was observed prior to sediment removal according to ITS (Fig. 6a, Table S2). During the intervention, the TP concentration first increased and thereafter

Table 4

Median values, test statistics and *P*-values (Wilcoxon rank-sum test) for water quality data from Lake Gallträsk before (1987–2005) and after suction dredging (2012–2024) annually (January–December) and during the growing season (June–September) for alkalinity, chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*), chemical oxygen demand (COD_{Mn}), watercolor, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH₄), the sum of nitrite and nitrate (NO₂₊₃), oxygen (O₂), pH, phosphate (PO₄), suspended solids (SS), total nitrogen (TN), the TN to total phosphorus (TP) ratio (TN/TP), TP, and turbidity. Suction dredging of L. Gallträsk was conducted in 2009–2011 following experimental dredging in 2006. Bolded values represent statistical significance ($P < 0.05$).

Parameter	Annual				Growing season			
	Median before	Median after	Test statistic	<i>P</i> -value	Median before	Median after	Test statistic	<i>P</i> -value
Alkalinity	0.7	0.6	640.0	0.027	0.7	0.6	269.0	0.001
Chl <i>a</i>	8.2	7.3	337.0	0.312	8.4	9.5	141.5	0.697
COD_{Mn}	11.0	13.0	249.5	<0.001	11.0	13.0	104.5	0.004
Color	42.5	56.0	351.5	0.01	40.0	44.0	142.0	0.170
EC	21.0	17.1	963.0	<0.001	21.0	16.9	362.5	0.001
NH ₄	20.2	20.0	367.0	0.913	13.0	8.5	172.5	0.092
NO₂₊₃	4.5	12.0	122.0	0.046	4.5	4.6	85.0	0.473
O ₂	8.1	8.6	476.0	0.322	8.1	8.6	153.5	0.294
pH	7.3	7.3	583.5	0.723	7.3	7.4	171.0	0.570
PO₄	2.8	1.5	457.5	0.025	2.9	1.5	214.0	<0.001
SS	4.0	2.5	736.5	0.004	4.0	3.1	237.5	0.214
TN	700.0	775.0	599.5	0.207	650.8	675.0	236.0	0.936
TN/TP	22.6	38.6	218.0	<0.001	21.6	30.6	65.0	<0.001
TP	34.8	19.0	1308.0	<0.001	35.0	22.8	406.5	<0.001
Turbidity	1.8	2.5	473.5	0.051	1.6	2.6	136.5	0.034

Fig. 3. Box plots presenting the minimum, lower quartile, median, upper quartile and maximum values of alkalinity (Alk), chemical oxygen demand (COD), watercolor, electrical conductivity (EC), the sum of nitrite and nitrate (NO₂₃), phosphate phosphorus (PO₄), suspended solids (SS), the total nitrogen to total phosphorus ratio (TN/TP), and total phosphorus (TP) in Lake Gallträsk before (1987–2005), during (2006–2011) and after (2012–2024) sediment removal. All annually available (January–December) and growing season data (June–September) are differentiated. Numbers of observations during the corresponding periods are presented above the boxes.

Fig. 4. Changes in all annually available observations of chemical oxygen demand (COD), water color, electrical conductivity (EC), oxygen (O_2), pH, phosphate phosphorus (PO_4), suspended solids (SS), total phosphorus (TP), and turbidity (Turb) in Lake Gallträsk before (1987–2005), during (2006–2011) and after (2012–2024) sediment removal according to structural break analysis. The black circles depict single observations, dashed black lines indicate linear regression and the solid red lines structural changes in the data with pink areas representing the 95 % confidence intervals of regression lines for different segments. Dashed vertical lines show the timing of biomanipulation in 2002 (gray) and suction dredging in between 2006 and 2011 (light blue). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

declined to the initial levels by the end of the period of sediment removal. In accordance with the results of structural break analysis, ITS suggested a lower level for the TP concentration after sediment removal. The mean absolute TP reduction with the intervention (blue line) was $3.1 \mu\text{g/L}$ (relative mean reduction 13.3 %) compared to a hypothetical situation without the intervention (red line). The trend terms during the interruptions (time1, time2) were significantly decreasing ($P < 0.05$) and the overall and pre-intervention trend (time) was decreasing at 0.1

significance level (Table S2). When interpreting the trend estimates, one must note that they are estimates of the logarithmic scale linear predictor (Eq. 3) and are additive. A significant change upwards in the TP concentrations was noted at the beginning of the intervention (interruption1). According to ITS, external loading (*load*) was not significant, whereas seasonality was. This implies that climate fluctuations (Fig. S4) did not affect TP concentrations and the lake is mainly subjected to internal loading.

Fig. 5. Changes in the growing season (June–September) chlorophyll *a* (Chl), ammonium (NH_4), phosphate phosphorus (PO_4), total nitrogen (TN), TN to total phosphorus (TP) ratio, and TP in Lake Gallträsk before (1987–2005), during (2006–2011) and after (2012–2024) sediment removal according to structural break analysis. The black circles depict single observations, dashed black lines indicate linear regressions and solid red lines structural changes in the data with pink areas representing the 95 % confidence intervals of regression lines for different segments. Dashed vertical lines show the timing of biomanipulation in 2002 (gray) and suction dredging between 2006 and 2011 (light blue). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

For SS, in turn, ITS suggested that there was no decreasing trend prior to sediment removal. The concentration during the implementation of sediment removal expectedly increased and markedly declined after the intervention in comparison with the hypothetical situation without sediment removal (absolute reduction of $3.2 \mu\text{g/L}$, relative mean reduction of 53.1 %) (Fig. 6b). There was also a significant change upwards in SS concentrations at the beginning of the suction dredging (interruption1) and a decreasing trend during the intervention period (time1, Table S2).

TN did not display significant changes during the study period according to ITS, which is consistent with the results of structural break analysis.

3.3. Biological quality elements

3.3.1. Phytoplankton

A massive phytoplankton fresh weight biomass of $35,163 \mu\text{g/L}$ was recorded in 1971 with a community dominated by Cyanophyceae (mainly *Microcystis aeruginosa*) and Chlorophyceae (e.g. *Desmodesmus* sp., *Chlamydomonas* sp.) (Fig. 7). In 2008, Cyanophyceae (*Dolichospermum* sp.) were still abundant (45 %) and the phytoplankton fresh weight biomass was $3900 \mu\text{g/L}$ indicating moderate ecological status for shallow humic lakes following the classification by Aroviita et al. (2019). In 2010 and 2011, during sediment removal, the fresh weight biomass was $1400 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $1300 \mu\text{g/L}$, respectively, indicating good ecological status.

Following sediment removal, the fresh weight biomass was at its highest in 2012, being $5428 \mu\text{g/L}$ and indicating poor ecological status. However, the proportion of cyanobacteria in the phytoplankton biomass was negligible and the community was dominated by Chrysophyceae (*Chrysococcus* spp., *Dinobryon* spp.) (Fig. 7). Ever since, the phytoplankton fresh weight biomass has mainly remained on a level below $1300 \mu\text{g/L}$, indicating high ecological status. The community has been dominated to a varying extent by Chlorophyceae (e.g. *Chlamydocapsa* sp., *Monoraphidium* sp., *Pediastrum* sp., *Tetraedron* sp.), Chrysophyceae (*Chrysococcus* spp., *Dinobryon* sp., *Pseudopedinella* sp.), Chryptophyceae (*Cryptomonas* sp.) and Dinophyceae (*Gymnodinium* sp., *Peridinium* sp.). The exception was the summer of 2016, when the fresh weight biomass ($3160 \mu\text{g/L}$) indicated moderate ecological status. However, the proportion of cyanobacteria was again very small (1.2 %), and the phytoplankton community was dominated by Conjugatophyceae (*Cosmarium* sp.).

The proportion of harmful cyanobacteria in the phytoplankton biomass was 73.0 % in 1971 and 45.0 % in 2008. During the period after sediment removal, it has fluctuated between 0 and 3.8 % indicating high ecological status (threshold level < 5 %; Aroviita et al., 2019). Likewise, the phytoplankton trophic index (Phillips et al., 2013) in L. Gallträsk has varied between -1.9 and 0.3 following sediment removal, indicating high ecological status (threshold level < 0.5; Aroviita et al., 2019).

3.3.2. Macrophytes

The abundance of emergent and floating-leaved aquatic

Fig. 6. ITS analysis results for total phosphorus (TP; a) and suspended solid (SS; b) concentrations in Lake Gallträsk based on annual observations in between 1987 and 2024. The blue line shows the trend before sediment removal (period 1987–2005) and gray lines the trend during the intervention (2006–2011). For the period after sediment removal (2012–2024), two alternative trends are presented: the blue line indicates the modeled trend without the intervention and the red line indicates the trend with the intervention. Light blue and pink areas denote the corresponding 95 % confidence intervals. Dashed vertical lines show the period of experimental dredging in 2006 and sediment removal in 2009–2011. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

macrophytes, mainly *N. lutea*, *Calla palustris*, and *Sparganium emersum* markedly increased throughout the L. Gallträsk area from the 1940s (Barkman, 2003). The most pronounced increase was observed in the coverage of *N. lutea*, which increased from 20 % in 1961 to 70 % in 1997 (Barkman, 1999; Barkman, 2003). During the 1950s and 1990s, endangered *Najas tenuissima* was observed in the southwestern part of the lake, but the species was considered to have vanished from the lake in the early 21st century (Issakainen et al., 2011).

Aquatic vegetation in 2002 before sediment removal was dominated by mosses (*Drepanocladus aduncus*, *Fontinalis antipyretica*) and submerged macrophytes (*Ceratophyllum demersum*), with floating-leaved macrophytes (*N. lutea*) still common, despite their annual harvesting (Fig. 8) (FCG, 2023). During sediment removal in 2010, *N. lutea* and mosses (*F. antipyretica*, *D. aduncus*, *D. tenuinervis*) were most abundant. In 2011, when macrophyte harvesting along transects had been conducted in conjunction with mapping, the abundance of *N. lutea* had

declined, *C. demersum* was exceptionally no longer observed along the transects, and *F. antipyretica* and *D. tenuinervis* were the most abundant species. During the years of sediment removal, a total of 15–20 species were recorded.

In 2014–2017, following sediment removal, when the lake was also intervened by harvesting within transects, *N. lutea*, *C. demersum*, *F. antipyretica* and *D. tenuinervis* were the most abundant species, with *Potamogeton natans* also being common. In 2020, the abundance of mosses had declined, whereas a dense population of *Myriophyllum verticillatum* together with a sparse population of invasive *Elodea canadensis* were for the first time observed. In 2022 and 2024, the abundances of both *M. verticillatum* and *C. demersum* had decreased, while *E. canadensis* considerably expanded. In 2024, *E. canadensis* was estimated to cover 60–70 % of the total lake area (Tanntu, 2024). *N. lutea* was still abundant, while the abundance of mosses was negligible. Additionally, *Chara virgata* was observed for the first time. The number of species recorded per year has varied between 10 and 17 following sediment removal. However, we stress that caution is needed in interpreting macrophyte data due to concomitant harvesting that occasionally occurred during the mapping (FCG, 2023).

3.3.3. Fishes

Fish species observed in sample fishing of L. Gallträsk during 1999, 2014, 2017, and 2021 were roach (*Rutilus rutilus*), perch (*Perca fluviatilis*), pike (*Esox lucius*), and crucian carp. The fish community was dominated by cyprinids based on both NPUE and BPUE (Fig. 9). The proportion of cyprinids in the total fish biomass was 75 % in 1999, 54 % in 2014, 73 % in 2017, and 24 % in 2021. On the contrary, the proportion of predatory fish (perch ≥ 15 cm together with pike) in the fish biomass was <20 % in 1999, 45 % in 2014, 20 % in 2017, and 27 % in 2021. However, it must be noted that gillnetting in 2014 and 2021 was conducted in late fall when fish activity is gradually declining due to colder water temperatures. Hence, the results may not fully represent the abundances and can only be treated as indicative of the fish community structure.

4. Discussion

4.1. Impacts of sediment removal on lake trophic status

Our study demonstrated that sediment removal substantially reduced TP and PO_4 concentrations in the water column of the small, shallow, urban Lake Gallträsk, which is well in line with other sediment removal studies (Ruley and Rusch, 2002; Van der Does et al., 1992; Xiang et al., 2024). The first marked decline in the TP concentration was recorded after sewage diversion. The reduction in external loading resulted in lower water column TP concentrations within a decade after sewage diversion, consistent with Jeppesen et al. (2005), who evaluated the response of northern hemisphere lakes subjected to reduced external P loads. However, the reduction in external loading alone was not sufficient for L. Gallträsk to fully recover, as the decline in TP concentrations during the growing season gradually levelled off by the late 1980s and stabilized to levels indicating eutrophy and moderate ecological status of the lake (average 49.7 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in 1987–2005 in the period before sediment removal) (Aroviita et al., 2019; Carlson, 1977). After sediment removal in 2009–2011, the growing season TP concentration in L. Gallträsk declined and stabilized to levels indicative of mesotrophy and good to high ecological status (average 22.7 $\mu\text{g/L}$) (Aroviita et al., 2019; Carlson, 1977).

Internal P loading can sustain primary production for years, even after a sufficient reduction in external loading. Due to legacy nutrients, lake recovery times can extend to decades (Abell et al., 2022; Scheffer et al., 1993; Steinman and Spears, 2020). Given the essential role of internal P loading in sustaining eutrophication, the removal of nutrient-rich sediments from lakes can be one of the most effective restoration methods, especially for small shallow lakes (Kiani et al., 2020). Positive

Fig. 7. Phytoplankton fresh weight biomass ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and the proportion of harmful cyanobacteria (a) and proportion of different taxa in the phytoplankton fresh weight biomass ($\mu\text{g/L}$) (b) in Lake Gallträsk during July–August in the years 1971–2024. Sediment removal was implemented in 2009–2011 following experimental dredging in 2006. The colored boxes in a) indicate the phytoplankton fresh weight biomass threshold values for the ecological status of small humic lakes (Aroviita et al., 2019).

Fig. 8. Abundance indexes of aquatic macrophyte types and number of species in total in Lake Gallträsk before (2002), during (2010–2011) and after sediment removal (2014–2024) with data retrieved from FCG (2023) and Tantt (2024). Harvesting of macrophytes along transects was conducted in 2011, 2014, 2017 and 2020 in conjunction with or before the mapping (FCG, 2023).

feedback of the ecosystem to sediment removal can be expected if internal P loading comprises a considerable proportion of the lake P budget, and if the amount of sediment removed is sufficient to reduce internal P loading (Jing et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2015; Phillips et al., 2015). The area subject to dredging in L. Gallträsk was only 18 % of the whole lake area. However, the dredging, which was intended to increase the lake depth most probably covered the (deeper) sediment accumulation area that usually concentrates higher amounts of releasable P (Tammeorg et al., 2022; Tammeorg et al., 2024c). Consequently, the release of P from the sediment in these areas probably contributed considerably to L. Gallträsk’s P budget, thus allowing for a decrease in

water column TP and PO_4 concentrations as a result of sediment removal. Our results support the proposition by Tammeorg et al. (2024a) that focusing dredging efforts on such hot-spot areas can be a cost-effective solution. However, the dynamics of internal P loading in lakes naturally vary depending on, for example, lake morphology, sediment biogeochemistry and environmental factors (e.g., Song and Burgin, 2017; Zhao et al., 2024). Hence, suitable locations, depths and extent of areas for sediment removal are always to be determined site-specifically.

The advanced recovery of L. Gallträsk due to sediment removal was supported by all the statistical methods used in this study, suggesting that the shift towards a more oligotrophic status without intervention would have been unlikely. Moreover, the insignificant impact of external TP loading after the sewage diversion, indicated by the ITS analysis, supports the conclusion that sediment removal alone had a substantial contribution to lake recovery. Due to the resistance of eutrophied lakes to perturbances (i.e., restoration), a shift from a turbid to a clear-water state may be difficult to achieve (Carpenter et al., 2001). Indeed, some studies have reported the return of TP concentrations to pre-sediment removal levels within a few years after intervention, especially if continued external loading has limited the longevity of the results (Kiani et al., 2020; Lürling et al., 2020; Ruley and Rusch, 2002) or the thickness of the removed sediment layer has been insufficient to reduce internal P loading (Liu et al., 2015).

In the case of L. Gallträsk, the external loading substantially decreased after sewage diversion in 1975. However, the lake is still subjected to excess external loading mainly originating from urban stormwaters, which can significantly impact surface water quality (e.g., Müller et al., 2020). Urban stormwater runoff positively correlates with surface water EC (Göbel et al., 2007), which could partly be reflected in

Fig. 9. Fish community composition in Lake Gallträsk based on a) the number of fish per gillnet (NPUE) and b) biomass of fish per gillnet (BPUE). In 2002 and 2017, gillnetting was conducted in July and August, respectively, and in 2014 and 2021, in November and October, respectively. The colored boxes indicate the threshold values for the ecological status of small humic lakes (Aroviita et al., 2019).

the elevated rates of change in EC in L. Gallträsk after sediment removal (Fig. 4), although the water column EC after sediment removal was in general significantly lower than before the intervention (Table 4). In addition to the possible contribution of external pollution, suction dredging itself can also increase water column EC after treatment, for example by promoting the release of heavy metals from the sediment (Zhang et al., 2010) or by increasing groundwater influx (Thomas et al., 2024). Indeed, a limited amount of data indicated slightly increased concentrations of heavy metals in L. Gallträsk after sediment removal, and a weak positive correlation between EC and Cd was observed (Fig. S5). However, as the concentrations of heavy metals in surface waters are also strongly connected to urban stormwater loading (Göbel et al., 2007), the cause of the elevated rate of change in EC after sediment removal remains uncertain. The possible contribution of urban stormwaters highlights the need to manage external loading to prevent further deterioration, although ITS suggested that TP and SS concentrations have been unaffected by external loading after sediment removal. Managing external loading is also a necessity in the context of climate change, which induces such changes in temperature and precipitation that are likely to run counter to reductions in nutrient loading (Jeppesen et al., 2005).

4.2. Stabilizing role of bottom-up and top-down forces

In L. Gallträsk, the proliferation of cyanobacteria has remained negligible following sediment removal, which is likely to reflect both resources (bottom-up) and predatory (top-down) forces. The rate of cyanobacterial production in eutrophic systems is determined by both P and N inputs and the ratio of these two elements (Hamilton et al., 2016; Paerl et al., 2016). A number of studies have stressed the importance of managing N in addition to P in lake restoration efforts (e.g., González Sagrario et al., 2005; Paerl et al., 2016), as N can play a significant role in determining trophic structure and sustaining water clarity in shallow lakes (González Sagrario et al., 2005). Nevertheless, the risk of cyanobacterial bloom formation increases at TP concentrations above 20–30 µg/L (Carvalho et al., 2013), and cyanobacteria generally benefit from a low TN/TP ratio (Li et al., 2021). In L. Gallträsk, the reduced TP concentration and increased TN/TP ratio (due to the insignificant impact on TN) after sediment removal is likely to have reduced the probability of cyanobacterial proliferation. In general, controlling N with sediment removal is more difficult than controlling P (Wan et al., 2025). The observed negligible impact of sediment removal on TN concentration in L. Gallträsk could be explained by denitrification, due to which surplus inorganic N in lakes is rather lost to the atmosphere than accumulated in the sediment (Jeppesen et al., 2005).

Decreases in primary limiting nutrients are the main contributors to temporal declines in phytoplankton biomass in Fennoscandian lakes and have the most pronounced impact on phytoplankton community composition (Paltsev et al., 2024). However, temporal changes in the phytoplankton community are also influenced by changes in organic carbon (OC), which has moderate to low importance for cyanobacteria, but positively correlates with cryptophytes and chlorophytes (Paltsev et al., 2024). In L. Gallträsk, increased values of water color and COD_{Mn} (as a proxy of OC; Kortelainen, 1993) were observed after sediment removal, which may have also partly affected the phytoplankton community. While the Chl *a* concentration (as a proxy of primary production) in L. Gallträsk was not affected by sediment removal and the subsequent TP reduction, changes in phytoplankton community composition from a dominance of cyanobacteria to cryptophytes, chlorophytes, and dinophytes may partly imply an effect of increased OC concentrations. Additionally, the increased availability of OC after sediment removal may have partly affected the availability of P resources in L. Gallträsk, as OC negatively correlates with the release of P from iron (Fe)-bound sedimentary P (Tammeorg et al., 2022).

The stabilization of P resources to lower levels after sediment removal with subsequent implications for phytoplankton communities

in L. Gallträsk was probably also promoted by changes in biological structure. In shallow lakes, the effectiveness of single restoration efforts can be hampered by nonlinear response trajectories mediated by interactions with biota (Abell et al., 2022; Jeppesen et al., 2012; Sarvala et al., 2020; Scheffer, 2004). Hence, a lack of combined measures targeted to affect multiple processes maintaining a eutrophied state has sometimes hindered the effectiveness of sediment removal (Jing et al., 2019). A sustainable improvement in lake status after restoration requires the re-establishment of in-lake processes improving and stabilizing water quality and ecological diversity (Moss, 1990; Scheffer et al., 1993). In L. Gallträsk, sediment removal and the subsequent reduction in the SS concentration enabled the recolonization of submerged macrophytes, allowing for the preservation of the achieved clear-water state. The suppression of phytoplankton by submerged macrophytes can be promoted, for example, by resource competition, zooplankton habitat provision, suppression of sediment resuspension, and excretion of allelopathic substances (Hupfer and Dollan, 2003; Mulderij et al., 2007; Scheffer et al., 1993; Vermaat et al., 2000).

In L. Gallträsk, the recolonization of submerged macrophytes was first initiated by *M. verticillatum* and *C. demersum* after sediment removal. However, the spread of invasive *E. canadensis* has accounted for the majority of submerged macrophyte re-establishment during recent years. *E. canadensis* poses environmental concern due to the risk of outcompeting native species (e.g., Mjelde et al., 2012). The continued spread of the species also hinders recreational use (Zehmsdorf et al., 2015). Additionally, the wide expansion of *E. canadensis* poses a potential risk of local anoxia or elevated pH peaks with subsequent pulses of sediment P to water, which are sometimes promoted by extremely dense *Elodea* stands (Sarvala et al., 2020). Consequently, we endorse continued monitoring of both macrophyte abundance and water quality in L. Gallträsk to assess the resilience of indigenous species to invasion and the stability of the achieved clear-water state, as well as to detect possible needs for future interventions. Nevertheless, we highlight that the re-establishment of submerged vegetation is critical to the sustainable restoration of algal-dominated lakes (e.g., Hofstra et al., 2024). Maintaining a sufficient abundance of submerged vegetation is necessary for the stability of a clear-water equilibrium in shallow lakes (Scheffer et al., 1993; Søndergaard et al., 2008; Triest et al., 2016), which may not be fully resilient and self-sustaining (Carpenter et al., 2001). Submerged macrophytes provide the highest biodiversity and facilitate the majority of the supporting ecosystem services in shallow lakes, due to which the trade-off between preserved natural value and hindered recreational use is to be accounted for (Janssen et al., 2021). Indeed, a high abundance of submerged macrophytes in shallow lakes is associated with good ecological status (Poikane et al., 2018), and the removal of submerged macrophytes at any scale larger than necessary is not recommended.

In addition to resources, algal control in lakes is mediated by predation and its cascading implications for lower trophic levels (e.g., Carpenter et al., 1985; Reynolds, 1984; Vanni and Findlay, 1990). Prior to sediment removal, a short-term, small-scale biomanipulation of crucian carp (85 kg/ha removed) was conducted in L. Gallträsk during 2003. When successful, the removal of planktivorous and benthivorous fishes can reduce the TP and Chl *a* concentrations in lakes (e.g., Hansson et al., 1998; Triest et al., 2016). However, the catch was low relative to the 200 kg/ha target, and there were no structural changes recorded in either TP or Chl *a* concentrations after biomanipulation, suggesting no significant impact of the intervention. Without repetition and high removal rates, the impacts of biomanipulation often cease without providing long-term water quality improvements (Søndergaard et al., 2007; Søndergaard et al., 2008).

While the fish community of L. Gallträsk since sediment removal has been dominated by cyprinids, piscivorous perch and pike have also been present (20–40 % of biomass). Cyprinids are often the dominant fish group in eutrophic lakes (e.g. Jeppesen et al., 2000; Olin et al., 2002), but a sufficient proportion of piscivorous fishes balances the food web

structure, with cascading impacts on lower trophic levels (Mehner et al., 2002). No data on zooplankton in L. Gallträsk were available, but a relatively low Chl *a* to TP ratio post-dredging (0.4) indicates a sufficient capability of zooplankton to regulate the phytoplankton biomass (Sarvala et al., 2020). Grazing zooplankton in L. Gallträsk are likely supported by the abundant submerged macrophytes, providing structural complexity and refugia against fish predation (Kuczyńska-Kippen and Joniak, 2016; Scheffer, 2004). To conclude, both the fish and macrophyte communities appear to support the adaptation L. Gallträsk to a new state of equilibrium. However, available biological data is rather descriptive due to data sparsity and inconsistency in sampling protocols and should thus be treated with caution in terms of evaluating success of water quality improvement. We highlight the importance of sufficient monitoring of biota with comprehensive resolution and consistent, standardized sampling protocols in future sediment removal studies, which is essential to allow for evaluating both successes and failures of restoration efforts (Moss, 2007).

Another factor that has potentially supportive impact on maintaining the current status of L. Gallträsk is the presence of *A. cygnea* in the lake. Mussels can have a significant role in the nutrient cycling of freshwaters (e.g., Atkinson and Vaughn, 2015). However, their contribution to the status of L. Gallträsk cannot be evaluated without information on their distribution and abundance.

4.3. Feasibility and profitability of sediment removal

While sediment removal may provide long-term water quality benefits, it also comes with environmental disadvantages including harmful water quality impacts, the resuspension of legacy contaminants, and the destruction of habitats and seed banks (Bormans et al., 2016; Knott et al., 2009; Lüring et al., 2020). Disturbances of flora and fauna are among the major environmental concerns associated with sediment removal. Unfortunately, no information is available on zoobenthos or mussels in L. Gallträsk to further assess the extent of ecological disturbances of sediment removal in the lake. However, recent studies in a small, shallow lake that underwent complete sediment removal demonstrated a relatively rapid recovery of the biota (macrophytes, zoobenthos, fishes), despite the significant disturbances (Tammeorg et al., 2024b).

Consistent with Bormans et al. (2016), increased turbidity and suspended solid, TP, and Chl *a* concentrations were observed in L. Gallträsk during the intervention. Additionally, a structural change in pH was observed, which was probably due to increased primary production. In contrast with other studies (Peterson, 1982), oxygen depletion was not observed during the intervention. However, COD_{Mn} together with water color increased in conjunction with sediment removal indicating browning, with concentrations remaining elevated ever since. In contrast, a meta-analysis of Chinese dredging projects by Xiang et al. (2024) revealed an initial increase in COD during dredging, but a steady decline thereafter. Our observation of increased COD_{Mn} (as a proxy of OC) during sediment removal is in line with Koelmans and Prevo (2003) suggesting that sediment perturbation can mobilize indigenous OC. Although Ruley and Rusch (2002) observed organic staining of lake waters post sediment removal following low rainfall, the reported effects of sediment removal on water color seem inconsistent (Wan et al., 2025).

In general, a trend of increased browning has been comprehensively reported for Finnish surface waters (Räike et al., 2024) and the water-color in Finnish lakes is mainly determined by OC (Xiao and Riise, 2021). Browning of L. Gallträsk is probably due to a combination of external and internal drivers. The water entering the lake from the two artificial ditches surrounding the southeastern bog is highly colored, which was also reported in 2008 (Issakainen et al., 2011), when elevated COD_{Mn} values were first observed (Fig. 4). Drainage of peatlands significantly increases OC export to surface waters (Finér et al., 2021; Härkönen et al., 2023). The impact of external drivers is supported by

the fact that the annual values of both color and COD_{Mn} after sediment removal were higher than during the growing season, indicating higher external OC loading during the periods of high runoff, when loading in general is higher (Fig. S3). However, a structural change was observed in water color and COD_{Mn} after sediment removal, suggesting that the increased values are not solely ascribed to increased inflow of humic substances. Previously, O'Connell et al. (2020) have reported an important legacy of humic-bound Fe complexes in sediment. The dredging-induced perturbation of L. Gallträsk probably initiated the mobilization of legacy OC from the sediment, following the findings of Koelmans and Prevo (2003). To some extent, the observed decline in EC during sediment removal could have partly affected the adsorption of OC onto inorganic particles and minerals, which is negatively related to EC (Groeneveld et al., 2020). However, the influence of sediment removal on the browning of L. Gallträsk requires further investigation. As the browning of surface waters has various ecological consequences (Blanchet et al., 2022; Creed et al., 2018; Solomon et al., 2015), we advocate including water color and COD_{Mn} in impact assessments of future sediment removal efforts.

The water content in the dredged sediment is substantial (Fört et al., 2025), which makes it difficult to handle and requires dewatering to achieve a high dry matter content and a sufficient reduction of harmful compounds in the filtrate (Simoni et al., 2024). Dewatering is also needed to decrease transportation and disposal costs and promote the sediment reusability (Yang et al., 2024). At L. Gallträsk, geotextile tubes combined with a synthetic flocculant were used for dewatering of the dredged sediment, with a marked impact on nutrient recovery from the sludge. More than 99 % of sludge TP and c. 97 % of TN were retained in the geotextile tubes. The filtrate that was returned to the lake did not contain higher concentrations of nutrients than the lake water itself. However, it should be noted that synthetic polymers in general can have negative environmental impacts due to the potential spread of nanoplastics and toxic compounds. Such impacts were not evaluated in L. Gallträsk. Nonetheless, we agree with Simoni et al. (2024) in suggesting that the use of biopolymers should be preferred in future applications to avoid potential negative environmental impacts and overcome possible limitations in the sediment reuse potential associated with synthetic polymers.

The handling and disposal of sediment elevates the operational expenses of sediment removal. Consequently, suction dredging is often mainly restricted to small lakes of high environmental value (Björk et al., 2010). In the 11.2-ha L. Gallträsk, the total costs of sediment removal in 2009–2011 were relatively high (€860,000 in total; €33/m³ of sediment removed). In comparison, the total costs of chemical precipitation using polyaluminium chloride in the 150-ha Finnish Lake Littoistenjärvi in 2017 were c. €229,000 (Sarvala et al., 2020). While the P inactivation instantly lowered the TP and Chl *a* concentrations in the water column of L. Littoistenjärvi (Sarvala et al., 2020), the lake has experienced slow re-eutrophication since the intervention and its estimated longevity is no more than 13 years (Sarvala and Helminen, 2023). In general, restoration efforts that mainly treat the symptoms of eutrophication (e.g., decreased oxygen concentration, increased cyprinid biomass) need regular repetition whereas nutrient removal closer to reference levels (e.g., following the WFD) may provide longer term results without a need for repeated interventions (Horppila, 2019). This was also seen in L. Gallträsk, where the high capital and operational expenses targeted at sediment removal promoted a shift towards re-oligotrophication, and no need for repeated interventions is currently foreseen. The costs of different restoration efforts can substantially affect the decision process, due to which the costly sediment removal may not always be considered as an option. The financial investments needed for different interventions are strongly case-sensitive and their assessment is a key component in system analysis guiding restoration (Tammeorg et al., 2024a). However, result longevity is also a substantial aspect to be considered in method selection as the cost-effectiveness of restoration efforts increase over time if future interventions are not required

(Suding and Gross, 2006). The financial investments required by lake restoration can also bring substantial economic benefits when successful in reducing the symptoms of eutrophication (Grizzetti et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2019). As concluded by Wan et al. (2025), sediment removal has potential for offering great ecological restoration but requires sufficient funding and cohesion in water governance with high demands for result longevity. While sediment removal appears to be a promising strategy especially for the small, shallow lakes, its profitability still needs to be developed to allow for wider application.

Possible reuse of sediment can provide possibilities of cost reimbursement in both dredging and sediment disposal (Fört et al., 2025) that should be accounted for in future applications. The recovery of and reuse of sediment nutrients, for instance, in fertilization, has potential for offering circular economic co-benefits (Haasler et al., 2024; Kiani et al., 2021; Kiani et al., 2023), hence addressing the need for increased P recycling and preventing the exhaustion of finite phosphate rock reserves (Dawson and Hilton, 2011). Additionally, the dredged sediment could be used in, for example, construction to replace traditional building materials (Fört et al., 2025). In L. Gallträsk, the use of dewatered sediment for fertilization was not an option due to elevated Zn and Pb concentrations, and the possibilities for reuse are always to be evaluated site-specifically. Consistent with the imperative of putting the land back on land (Canfield et al., 2024), the dewatered sediment of L. Gallträsk was used in land construction.

5. Conclusions

Sediment removal in L. Gallträsk appears to have been the perturbation needed to break down the resilience of its turbid, eutrophic state. Additionally, sediment removal appeared to enable the recolonization of the submerged macrophyte community, which supports the sustaining of the clear-water state achieved following nutrient reduction. In addition to the impact of the decline in TP and PO₄ concentrations, the phytoplankton community in L. Gallträsk could have partly been affected by the long-term increase in lake water color and COD_{Mn} after sediment removal. These increases were a somewhat surprising observation, calling for further studies to evaluate the influence of sediment removal on lake browning. Our results emphasize the need for comprehensive, long-term monitoring activities post-intervention that allow for a reliable impact assessment. While the results currently indicate no need for further in-lake measures for L. Gallträsk, attention must be paid to managing the external loading within tolerable boundaries, which is a fundamental prerequisite for maintaining the achieved status.

Our results imply that the promotion of long-term lake recovery requires a paradigm shift from nutrient retention to nutrient recovery from sediments in lake restoration. The findings of the current study indicate L. Gallträsk as an encouraging example of successful lake restoration with potential for guiding future interventions in small, shallow lakes. Our results suggest that targeting sediment removal to such relatively small areas, that accumulate high amounts of releasable P, can contribute considerably to the reduction of internal P loading. Revealing suitable areas for dredging can provide further application perspectives for this promising lake restoration approach. However, we underline that each lake is unique and targeting sediment removal efforts are always to be determined site-specifically considering the lake characteristics, dynamics of internal loads, potential harm to the environment, and the financial investments needed. While sediment removal can act as a tool for sustainable lake restoration by providing a needed nudge towards re-oligotrophication, the profitability of dredging, sediment handling and disposal needs to be developed in order to allow for this method to become a mainstream approach in lake restoration. Reframing of sediments as possible sources of nutrients and alternative materials can provide potential for circular economic co-benefits.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Laura H. Härkönen: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Antti Taskinen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Olga Tammeorg:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Anna-Lena Granlund-Blomfelt:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Data curation.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The authors declare that no generative AI or AI-assisted technologies were used in the writing process.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2025.107715>.

Data availability

The water quality and phytoplankton data presented in the article are mostly available from an open database of the Finnish Environment Institute (License CC BY 4.0, <https://www.syke.fi/en/environmental-data/open-web-services/environmental-data-apis>). Fish and macrophyte data will be provided upon request.

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